

Family and Social Relationship in Arthur Miller's Play "The Price"

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Abstract

For family relationships, the present paper takes into account Miller's one of the significant plays The Price (1968). Post World War II America faced new challenges. The common questions which became prominent were the growing disintegration in the marital life of Americans and the fear of another world war. The responsibility in marriage was the critical issue to be dealt with by the dramatists of the time. The revival of the family ethos was the cry of the day. Arthur Miller, the family healer, presented this question in The Price (1968) and the plays published in 1968.

Family is the basic unit of the social system which guarantees security and well being of an individual. In fact, "it [family] is the key social unit within where we learn to love, come to terms with our aggressions, develop a conscience, and acquire values". Miller, throughout his life, remained influenced by the Greek tradition of Social Drama. He felt that the relationship between man and society is the primary concern of man as far as human life in general and family life, in particular, is concerned.

Keywords: Family relationship, Marriage, Society, Human life.

For family relationships, the present paper takes into account Miller's one of the significant plays The Price (1968). Post World War II America faced new challenges. The common questions which became prominent were the growing disintegration in the marital life of Americans and the fear of another world war. The responsibility in marriage was the key issue to be dealt with by the dramatists of the time. The revival of the family ethos was the cry of the day. Arthur Miller, the family healer, presented this question in The Price (1968) and the plays published in 1968.

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Miller's plays highlight the pathetic condition of the contemporary family life of the American middle class. Miller was "a preacher who sermonizes on the pathetic martyrdom of an oppressed middle class." Due to Miller's emphasis on family and society, it is generally assumed that he is a social critic and thinker who tries to unearth the multiple threads of social and adheres to any 'line,' whether political or ideological. Nevertheless, he bears a quasi-Marxist stamp, and most of his plays tend to become partisan social critique". Miller was concerned with the welfare of the individual. He delivers the message that relations between individual, family, society, and state should be cordial and harmonious. He explores and investigates the causes which vitiate the cordiality and harmony in human relations.

Major concern of Miller's plays is industrial and commercial society on the one hand, and family on the other. His endeavor in his plays is to reconcile public and private postures of modern man. In *All My Sons*, *Death of a Salesman* and *The Price* one of the characters is shown as committed to the family – Joe Keller, Willy Loman, and Victor respectively. However, the drive for success and material prosperity in a competitive society causes disintegration of family set-up, and family relations suffer severe jolt and shock. From the perusal of the plays, it becomes crystal clear that only genuine love, loyalty, compassion and piety, and moral responsibility in human relations can stop the erosion of cordial family relationships and damage caused by industrial-commercial pressures of society. Material success is achieved for the welfare of the family. But this material success takes place at the cost of moral responsibility towards society. The magical spell of the capitalist system which nurtures false illusions of success is akin to the cobweb which strangulates the head of the family. Miller does attack the capitalist system, but his tone is diplomatic. He attacks the capitalist system in the guise of "liberal parable hidden under social responsibility." Miller imparts excellent importance to the concept of family, and rightly so because family is the basic and primary unit of human society.

The existence of an individual is based on family and society. Family and society provide safety and security to the individual. The individual should treat both family and community as his home. One must be amenable to change in oneself and society. Man has a subjective as well as objective existence which stretches from individual to family, and family to the community. The individual is an integral part of society.

Further, society plays a dominant and decisive role in the life of the individual. Culture is inside of man and man is inside of the community, and you cannot even create a truthfully drawn psychological entity on the stage until you understand his social relations and their power to make him what he is and prevent him from being what he is not. The fish is in the water, and the water is in the fish.

The Price is the play which centers around the familial conflict which disintegrates familial values. It shows that the father's money-minded attitude brings disaster in the family, which is the leading cause of discord between the two sons, Victor and Walter. The play depicts the Depression only as a vehicle to unravel the father's materialistic attitude. The father in this play hovers like a ghost in the memories of his two sons. As the play opens, we find two brothers – Victor and Walter – meeting after a gap of sixteen years to settle the family affairs and to dispose of their parental furniture. Their meeting takes the shape of a dispute, and the meeting which was to decide the price of the parental furniture includes the issues of several other costs – the price for filial loyalty, successful career, happy marriage, and breaking family ties.

In the materialistic society, the feelings and emotions of love, loyalty, and sacrifice have lost their fragrance. Even the smallest unit of society, that is, the family is also corrupted by money, which makes man treacherous, self-centered, and disloyal to those who have done a lot for his well being. *The Price* is the continuation of *All My Sons* and *Death of a Salesman*, but in this play, we

find a change in Miller's attitude towards family relationships. In this play, we see the progress in Miller's views in the sense that for the discord in familial ties only society is not to blame, rather human nature and human imperfections also play a significant role.

The Price tries to dramatize the theme that man is responsible for his actions and their outcome. A man should take responsibility for his decisions rather than merely cursing society. The arguments between the brother's point out their differences on the issues like responsibility, love, and loyalty within the family relationship: "Responsibility is a kind of love. It's the only thing that prevents total slaughter, violence, and nihilism".

In the play, Victor is the only character who has a sense of responsibility for his family. When his family is in the grip of Economic Depression, he comes forward to help it. He sacrifices his studies and joins the police force to support his family financially. However, it is the fact that later in life, he feels that his sacrifice has gone waste. This desperation finds an outlet when he talks to his wife Esther, and says, "I'll be frank with you, kid – I look at my life, and the whole thing is incomprehensible to me. I know all the reasons and all the reasons and all the reasons, and it ends up – nothing". Walter, on the other hand, does not take any responsibility and has a materialistic bent of mind. He is self-centered and refuses to sacrifice his aim in life for the sake of his family, which is facing a tough time because of Depression. Walter establishes himself as a well-known surgeon and earns millions of dollars. The ghost of failure makes him ill, and as he recovers from his illness, he finds that in the pursuit of materialistic success, he estranged himself from the familial bonds. He finds himself alone and isolated. He realizes that without the cordial family ties, life is barren and dry like the wasteland. Thus, the blind race for material gain ends in the disharmony of family relationships – father-mother, father-son, brother-brother, and husband-wife.

In the discussion about their past life, Walter reveals that their father had 4000 dollars with him at the time of Economic Depression. Thus, he tries to shatter the illusion of Victor's sacrifice for the sake of the family. Walter tries to dismantle the illusion and pressurize Victor to face the reality that there was no feeling of love in the family, and Victor's attitude of sacrifice was merely his illusion to run away from reality. As far as family relations between Victor's father and mother are concerned, there was lack of warmth of love and loyalty. Walter says, "There was no love in this house. There was no loyalty. There was nothing here but a straight financial arrangement".

The Price has been paid by Victor and Walter for their deeds. Victor has paid the price for his sense of loyalty and duty towards his father; while Walter has paid the price for his materialistic attitude. He is lonely and isolated from familial ties. He is also under mental depression due to his broken marriage. He has lost his peace of mind. In this play, two main approaches to life have been discussed in detail – moral and material. It is true that Walter has achieved success in the materialistic sense, but he lacks Victor's moral responsibility towards family. Too much stress on personal gains makes Walter selfish and self-centred. He does not bother about the welfare of his parents and brother. The basic question is "to find an interpretation of existence which depends neither on a naive endorsement of human perfectibility or a cynical pose of alienation. The real problem lies in acknowledging the imperfection of man and the inadequacy of society and yet continuing to place faith in the human potential".

Family relations are based on material considerations. Victor's father betrays him by concealing the information that he had 4000 dollars with him. But Victor is a loyal son who tries to defend his father when he says, "I just didn't want him to end up on the grass. And he didn't. That's all it was, and I don't need anything more" (Miller, *The Price* 92). In the play, the attitude of the wives is also materialistic. Victor and Walter's mother and Victor's wife are a case in point. As Walter says, "There was nothing here but a straight financial arrangement. . . . She [mother] said a hundred times that her marriage destroyed her musical career. They [parents] were never lovers".

The emphasis in *The Price*, father-son relationship has been discussed in a new perspective. The play shows that in the father-son relationship, the father's role is not always laudable. Franz betrays his son Victor by concealing the information of money that was with him during the Depression. Franz's money-minded attitude plays havoc with the career of his son, Victor. He could not pursue his university education.

In *The Price*, Victor is left with no option. He is on the verge of his retirement. The revelation from Walter's mouth that there was no need of Victor's sacrifice for the sake of family because their father had enough money to run the family at the time of Depression has no value for Victor as he has spent the best part of his life in the job of a policeman. Miller's earlier conception that family is a sustaining force for society seems to be shattered as all the members of the family except Victor are motivated by materialistic ends. There is no feeling of genuine love for the family. Even parents are themselves indulged in betrayal. As far as family relations between Victor's mother and father are concerned, they lacked the warmth of love and loyalty. As Walter tells Victor: ". . . There was no love in this house. There was no loyalty. There was nothing here but a straight financial arrangement. . . . She [mother] said a hundred times that her marriage destroyed her musical career. They [parents] were never lovers".

As regards the relationship between brothers in *The Price*, Victor recognizes and epitomizes the value of filial and human relations, the value of love and loyalty, but Walter is a foil to Victor who represents the value of money and dream of success at the cost of duties and responsibilities towards the welfare of the family. Victor is the icon of moral and ideal responsibility towards family, whereas Walter shirks the same, and stands for money and prosperity and material gains for one's success and benefit only. Victor stands for idealistic attitude towards family, but Walter represents a pragmatic attitude which stands for self-centered and selfish and individualistic approach caring little for love and loyalty towards the family. Victor embodies moral responsibility towards family and society, which may be treated as the main trait of "the whole man". Victor is quite aware of the fact that as a police officer, he has performed his job towards society in a responsible and manner.

In *The Price* seem to be tied by a similar thread, which is the extension of Miller's approach towards fraternal relationship. The family undergoes the same trauma due to the economic depression of 1929. In the play, we have brothers –one who is loyal to family and the other who is prone to self-interest. Victor (*The Price*) sacrifices his interests in favour of the family by leaving the college studies to help the family during Depression. Walter (*The Price*) represents the category of selfish and self-centered sons who leave their home in search of better opportunities without caring for the interest of the family. Here the moral responsibility is abandoned in favor of selfish ends. In this play economic disaster tells upon the financial and spiritual health of the head of the family, that is, father; and the mother in this play instead of showing sympathy towards the husband, criticizes her husband's failure in business. In *The Price*, the wife's reaction to husband's failure in business in Victor's words is of a very unpleasant nature:

While comparing Victor and Walter, it may be said that from a material point of view, Victor is loser and Walter is the victor. But as far as a moral obligation toward father and family is concerned, Victor is victor and Walter is loser. In brief, we come across the theme of guilt and betrayal in *The Price*. Drive for success in the thematic concerns affects the relations among the members of the family, and we can safely conclude that family and societal concerns are intertwined to the extent that they cannot be treated as isolated from each other. Family relations affect societal relations and vice versa.

Welland rightly remarks that "the frictions of family life" are related "to those of the macrocosm outside: his [Miller's] families live in a recognizably real world" (2-3). Miller has used the analogy of interrelationship between fish and water to describe the interrelationship between individual

and society. This analogy means “serious treatment of a human being must encompass the society that surrounds him or her as the force that has conditioned thoughts, culture, attitudes, and values” .Relationship between individual and society is the same as we notice between fish and water. Fish cannot exist and survive without water; similarly, individuals cannot exist and survive without society.

Further, fish is surrounded by water, and the individual is surrounded by the socio-economic and political phenomenon of society. Modern tragedy emanates from the conflicts and clash of values between individuals and their socio-economic environment. Man’s situation is either threatening the survival of the individual or promising him security.

Social surroundings, when threatening, generate conflict in family relationships as we notice in *The Price*. Family is the smallest fundamental unit of society which reflects broader concerns of nation: “. . . The larger society is reflected by the little society of the family. That little society, that microcosm, Miller knew intimately and revealingly documented”. As far as the concept of “whole man” is concerned, the protagonist has to be judged both about family and society.

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